

Measurement uncertainty: impact of sub-sampling of the test portion and of preparation of the initial suspension

Study of test portion size : comparison 10g *versus* 25g

Report - Version 1 – 07/03/2017

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2 INTRODUCTION

The food legislation defines quantitative criteria for coagulase positive staphylococci (CPS) and *Listeria monocytogenes* (Lm) in food (EC Regulation 2073/2005 modified (criteria 2.2.3, 2.2.4, 2.2.5, 2.2.7 & 2.4.1 in Annex I, Chapter 2 for CPS and criteria 1.2 and 1.3 in Annex I, Chapter 2 for Lm). Analyses related to these quantitative criteria require control of the measurement uncertainty (MU) associated with sampling and the analytical method applied. Without knowledge about the MU, or if the MU is ignored in the interpretation of results, a wrong conclusion may be drawn. For example, the analytical result based on the plate counts may comply with the limit set in the microbiological criterion whereas the true result (lying in the uncertainty range) may not comply. A correct interpretation of analytical results, in terms of conformity with regulatory limits, thus requires the knowledge of MU associated to these results as well as the limitation of this uncertainty as far as possible.

Food sampling and subsampling is recognized as a major source of MU, in particular for solid matrices characterized by heterogeneous bacterial contaminations. The new version of the EN ISO Standard 6887-1, which will be published soon, describes different options for preparation of samples before analysis, including preparation of subsamples, pooled samples and composited samples. In the series of Standards EN ISO 6887-2 to 5 on the preparation of test samples for microbiological analyses of different types of food matrices, it is not specified how to subsample the test portion within the laboratory sample (sample that is sent to the laboratory).

The purpose of this study was to contribute to harmonization of food sampling procedures of subsampling the test portion within solid matrices, that (i) reduce the overall MU, (ii) better ensure that the contamination of a sample is correctly reflected in the test portion taken and analyzed, and (iii) is feasible to carry out with standard laboratory equipment.

The outcome of this study will be transferred to ISO/TC 34/SC 9 (i) to provide data for the revision of CEN ISO/TS 19036 (MU estimation for quantitative determinations), and to quantify the MU part linked to subsampling of test portions for solid matrices, (ii) to provide data for the next revision of EN ISO 6887 series to better define the procedure of test portion subsampling in solid matrices.

3 CONTEXT

3.1 PRELIMINARY STUDIES

Prior studies had been performed in our laboratory on the enumeration of the mesophilic microflora at 30°C, of Lm and of CPS showing the importance of the test portion size for analysis representativeness and value of measurement uncertainty (unpublished result). A 100-g test portion revealed to be more representative of the sample than a 10-g test portion, and it allowed reducing MU. Standard EN ISO 6887-1 prescribing 10-fold dilution of the sample during the preparation of the initial suspension, the preparation of an initial suspension from a 100-g test portion would lead to perform several successive dilutions since the blender bag classically used in a microbiological laboratory can contain a maximum of 400 ml. Such a test portion size would be hardly feasible in routine, and would lead to a financial additional burden and technical difficulties for the laboratories.

3.2 OBJECTIVES

Using food matrices naturally contaminated by CPS and/or Lm, the objective of this study was to compare on the one hand, the CPS enumeration results and on the other hand, those for Lm performed from a test portion size of 25 g and 10 g. This would allow to show (or not) an improvement on the representativeness of the sample to be analysed from a 25-g test portion *versus* a 10-g test portion (which is the portion size given in Regulation 2073/2005 today), and a reduction of MU on the analysis. The variation in the experimental data was assessed using both deterministic and stochastic analyses in order to obtain as good information about the measurement uncertainty as possible.

To analyse a test portion of 10 g and 25 g, the implementation of one dilution step is sufficient to obtain an initial suspension diluted 10-fold, which is conceivable in routine, contrary to a 100-g analysis. This study should allow selecting the most pertinent test portion size, in order to obtain a satisfactory MU associated with the chosen subsampling technique.

4 MATERIALS AND METHODS

EURL *Lm* and EURL CPS proposed a collaborative study with the respective NRLs networks. The volunteers who accepted to participate compared the results of enumeration with a test portion of 10 g and a test portion of 25 g (see the experimental protocol in annex). The results had to be sent back to the two EURLs by the end of February 2016.

4.1 MATERIAL

For *Lm*, food matrices were ready-to-eat matrices, to be tested in the frame of the EC Regulation n°2073/2055 amended, belonging to the categories « RTE », naturally contaminated with *Listeria monocytogenes*. As the concentration of *Lm* is stable at -18°C, samples can be stored several months at -18°C before analysis. The minimal required mass of each sample was 250 g.

For CPS, the food matrices to be tested in the frame of the EC Regulation n°2073/2055 amended were included in the categories « milk and milk products » and « shelled and shucked products of cooked crustaceans and molluscan shellfish ». The minimal required mass of each sample was 250 g.

4.2 PREPARATION OF SAMPLES

From each food sample of naturally contaminated matrix, 10g sample portion size were taken by combining material from 5 spots, and correspondingly for 25g sample portion size. Each action was repeated 5 times to get 5 test portions of 10 g each or 25 g each.

4.3 METHOD FOR LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES

Lm enumeration was performed once (no repetition of the analysis) by following the standardised method (EN ISO 11290-2 with amendment) or a validated commercial method. Required material and culture media are described in the protocols or standards.

4.4 METHOD FOR COAGULASE POSITIVE *STAPHYLOCOCCUS*

CPS enumeration was performed once (no repetition of the analysis) by following a standardised method (EN ISO 6888-1 or EN ISO 6881-2) or a validated commercial method. Required material and culture media are described in the protocols or standards.

4.5 STATISTICAL TOOLS

4.5.1 DETERMINISTIC ASSESSMENT

The log mean and variance of positive samples were calculated for each matrix and sample portion size using Excel. The ratios of log mean and variance for 10 and 25 gram sample portion size were calculated and interpreted as described below.

4.5.2 PROBABILISTIC MODELLING

The normal distribution was fitted to \log_{10} (cfu/g) data, the mean and the standard deviation were estimated. Figure 1 illustrates a set of five values and the normal distribution associated to the values. The `fitdist` function of `fitdistrplus` R package (Pouillot & Delignette, 2010) was used to estimate standard deviation and mean when none of the five values was censored. When at least one value was below the enumeration limit, the `fitdiscend` function of the same package was used to estimate mean and standard deviation.

Figure 1. Density of lognormal distribution (grey line) associated to five enumeration values (squares)

As the objective was to compare variances associated to measurand of 10 and 25g, the two datasets associated to a food were modelled independently (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Density of lognormal distribution for five 10 g (blue) and five 25 g (red) measurands.

In order to estimate the difference of uncertainty according to the two measurands, the ratio R of variances (σ^2) obtained for the two test portion masses was used:

$$R = \frac{\sigma_{25g}^2}{\sigma_{10g}^2}$$

R values below one indicated that variance associated to cfu counts in 25g sub-sample was lower than for 10g.

Uncertainty on (σ^2) was estimated with parametric bootstrap (bootdistcens function of fitdistrplus R package, 10000 iterations). Figure 3 shows the uncertainty on normal distribution associated to a dataset. The uncertainty was estimated by Monte-Carlo simulation.

Figure 3. Densities of lognormal distribution estimated by parametric bootstrap for the distribution presented in Figure 2.

5 RESULTS

5.1 RESULTS FOR *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* EXPERIMENTS

5.1.1 ANALYSED SAMPLES – RAW DATA

Five laboratories located in France, Czech Republic, Norway and Slovakia (1 EURL, 3 NRLs and another laboratory) collected and analysed samples in the frame of this study.

Twelve samples of seven different matrixes were analysed. The obtained data are shown in Figure 4 and Table 1.

A 1-2 log unit difference between subsample counts was observed for all sample matrixes both for 10 and 25 gram test portion sizes (Figure 4). Some subsamples contained concentrations of *L. monocytogenes* below the enumeration limits; 4 samples for 10 g test portion size and 3 samples for 25 gram test portion size. Two of these samples, cheese (sample 2) and heat treated chicken meat (sample 12), had also subsample counts both below the enumeration limit and more than 2 log units higher than this limit. The large differences indicate a large heterogeneity of *Listeria* concentrations in the samples.

Figure 4. Measured counts of *L. monocytogenes* in 10 subsamples of food matrix, 5 obtained with 10 gram portion size and 5 with 25 gram portion size. The sample numbers refer to Table 1.

Table 1. Data for samples and subsamples in terms of detected *L. monocytogenes*, log means of *L. monocytogenes* counts and variances for 10 and 25 gram portion sizes, as well as ratios of log means and variances for 10 and 25 gram portion sizes. Variance ratios above 1.0 indicate a higher value for 25 gram portion size than for 10 gram portion size.

Sample number	Sample type	Subsamples above enumeration level		Log mean (log cfu/g)		Log mean ratio	Variance (δ^2)		Variance ratio
		10 g	25 g	10 g	25 g		10 g	25 g	
		10 g	25 g	10 g	25 g	25/10 g	10 g	25 g	25/10 g
1	Fresh cheese of sheep	5	5	2,24	2,34	1,04	0,0051	0,0024	0,47
2	Cheese	3	4	2,67	2,52	0,94	NA	NA	NA
3	Salami	0	1	NA	1,48	NA	NA	NA	NA
4	Hash-and-crums sausage	3	2	1,495	1,45	0,97	NA	NA	NA
5	Meat delicatessen (meat jelly)	5	5	2,28	2,14	0,94	0,49	0,15	0,31
6	Andouille	5	5	3,68	3,62	0,98	0,14	0,08	0,57
7	Andouille	5	5	3,37	3,31	0,98	0,023	0,36	15,65
8	Andouille	5	5	3,73	3,59	0,96	0,013	0,012	0,92
9	Andouille	5	5	4,1	3,93	0,96	0,35	0,12	0,34
10	Andouille	5	5	3,57	3,53	0,99	0,038	0,064	1,68
11	Heat treated chicken meat*	5	5	0,85	0,71	0,84	0,85	1,2	1,41
12	Heat treated chicken meat*	4	3	1,69	1,04	0,62	NA	NA	NA

*enumeration limit 2 cfu/g

Nine of the analysed samples had at least one subsample with more than 100 cfu/g of *L. monocytogenes*, which is the legal limit according to EC Regulation 2073/2005. For one sample (number 11), counts above 100 cfu/g were observed only with 25 gram test portion size. For the remaining eight samples, subsample counts above 100 cfu/g were observed both for 10 and 25 gram test portion sizes.

The measured log mean counts for 10 and 25 gram sample portion sizes were in the ranges 0.85-4.1 and 0.71-3.93 log cfu/g, respectively, indicating a similar range for both test portion sizes, but with a shift downwards of approximately 0.14 log units for 25 gram portion sizes compared to 10 gram test portion sizes.

The variance was estimated only for samples with 5 positive results. The variances for all samples ranked from a minimum value 0.0024, obtained for fresh cheese, to maximum value 1.2, obtained for heat treated chicken meat. Both extreme values were obtained with 25 gram test portion size.

5.1.2 RATIOS BETWEEN TEST PORTION SIZES (DETERMINISTIC APPROACH)

The difference of the two test portion sizes was investigated by comparing the ratios of log mean counts and variance for 25 g and 10 g portion size (25/10 g) (see Table 1 and Figure 5). Ratios equal to 1.0 indicate no difference, ratios higher than 1.0 that the values were higher for 25 gram than for 10 gram test portion size, and vice versa for ratios below 1.0. The results are shown in Table 1 and Figure 5.

The ratios of log mean counts were below 1.0 for all samples, indicating lower counts for 25 gram test portion size than for 10 gram. The difference was however small, i.e. within 7% for all samples except for chicken samples. For these two samples, the means were respectively 20 and 63% higher for 10 g test portion size than for 25 g. The deviation was due to high peak values for one or two subsamples (Figure 4).

The ratio of variance was observed higher than 1.0 for four samples and below 1.0 for four samples. For the four remaining samples, the variance could not be estimated due to subsamples results below the enumeration level. The extreme ratios of variances were 0.031 and 15.65 log units (Tables 1 and 2), obtained for meat delicatessen and andouille, respectively. The ratios of variances varied more than for log means, and there was no systematic pattern.

Figure 5. Ratios of 25 gram and 10 gram portion sizes for log mean values and variances (σ^2) of 5 positive subsamples based on standard analyses of raw data in Excel.

Based on the analysis of raw data, no clear differences between portion sizes could be seen for variance, while a small but systematically higher mean count was seen for 10 gram portion size than for 25 gram portion size.

5.1.3 ANALYSES OF VARIANCE TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE UNCERTAINTIES OF VARIANCE (PROBABILISTIC APPROACH)

To explore whether the ratios of variances described above were really different from 1.0 or only appeared different, parametric bootstrap was used to estimate the variances (σ^2) with an uncertainty. The method take data below enumeration level and other uncertainties into account, assuming that the counts below the detection limit is in the range between the detection limit for qualitative analysis (1 cfu per 25 gram) and the enumeration limit for quantitative analysis (1 cfu per 10 or 2 gram, depending on the assay applied).

The ranges of variance were estimated for all samples, both for 10 and 25 gram portion sizes. Results for four of the samples are given in Figure 6 as illustration of the different patterns, the remaining in Annex 2. The samples gave different patterns. Some showed small difference between portion sizes in terms of log mean value and variance, but with a high variance (upper left), while others gave a different log mean but a small and similar variance for the two portion sizes, visualized as shifted peaks (upper right). The two other samples gave different log mean values and variances, sometimes highest for 25 gram portion size (lower left) and sometimes for 10 gram portion size (lower right).

Simulation outputs for four samples – range of variation

Figure 6. Estimated log mean counts and ranges of variance for four samples for 10 g (blue line) and 25 g (red line) portion sizes using parametric bootstrap

The ratios of variances between 10 and 25 gram portion sizes, taking the uncertainty of variance into account, are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Ratios of variances for 10 versus 25 gram portion sizes, with the uncertainty of variances taken into account

The results showed that the ratios of variance between 10 and 25 gram portion sizes are significantly different in only two samples; sample 7 (andouille) and 11 (heat treated chicken meat). Both these samples had one or more subsamples of 25 gram portion size with approximately one log higher counts than all the other subsamples (Figure 4).

The results from parametric bootstrap indicated that the variances between the portion sizes were even less different than observed with deterministic statistical analyses.

5.2 RESULTS FOR COAGULASE POSITIVE STAPHYLOCOCCI (CPS) EXPERIMENTS

5.2.1 ANALYSED SAMPLES – RAW DATA

Twelve laboratories located in France, Czech Republic, Cyprus, Hungary, Italy and Slovakia (1 EURL, 6 NRLs and 5 other laboratories) collected and analysed samples in the frame of this study.

Thirty-four samples of cheeses and other dairy products were analysed using EN ISO 6888-1 or EN ISO 6888-2. The counts of all samples and subsamples are shown in Figure 8 and Table 3.

The samples had counts in the range from 10 (log 1) to 70 000 000 (log 7) cfu/g. The highest counts were observed in samples 20, 29 and 30, all being cheeses. These samples were also the samples with smallest difference between the lower and the higher subsample counts, 0.4 log units. The differences between subsamples were otherwise within 1.0 log unit for 13 samples and within 2.0 log units for most other samples. The ranges of counts between subsamples were

similar for 10 and 25 gram test portion sizes. The results indicated a large heterogeneity within some, but not all, samples.

Subsamples with counts below the enumeration level were observed for only three samples, but found both for 10 and 25 gram test portion sizes (Table 2). The enumeration limit for EN ISO 6888-1 is 100 cfu/g while for EN ISO 6888-2, it is 10 cfu/g.

Figure 8. Measured counts of CPS in 10 subsamples of food matrix, 5 obtained with 10 gram portion size and 5 with 25 gram portion size. The sample numbers refers to Table 3.

Table 2. Data obtained for samples and subsamples in terms of detected CPS, log means of CPS counts and variances for 10 and 25 gram portion sizes, as well as ratios of log means and variances for 10 and 25 gram portion sizes. Variance ratios above 1.0 indicate a higher value for 10 gram portion size than for 25 gram portion size.

Sample number	Sample type	Subsamples above enumeration level		Log mean (log cfu/g)		Log Mean ratio	Variance		Variance ratio
		10 g	25 g	10 g	25 g	25/10 g	10 g	25 g	25/10 g
1	Cheese	5	5	4,68	5,04	1,08	0,32	0,11	0,33
2	Cheese	5	5	3,26	2,88	0,88	0,026	0,59	23,00
3	Cheese	1	2	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
4	Cheese	5	5	4,37	4,34	0,99	0,55	1,86	3,36
5	Cheese	5	5	4,73	4,83	1,02	0,15	0,07	0,48
6	Outbreak milk product**	5	5	4,67	4,83	1,04	0,08	0,16	2,00
7	Outbreak milk product**	5	5	5,59	5,63	1,01	0,17	0,02	0,13
8	Outbreak milk product**	5	5	4,98	4,94	0,99	0,05	0,03	0,68
9	Outbreak milk product**	5	5	5,40	5,69	1,05	0,08	0,09	1,13
10	Fromage frais	5	5	3,56	3,48	0,98	0,03	0,01	0,33
11	Faisselle	4	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
12	Goat Tome	5	5	4,61	4,40	0,95	0,06	0,04	0,69
13	Fromage blanc	5	5	3,17	3,26	1,03	0,05	0,03	0,64
14	Fromage frais	5	5	3,93	3,98	1,01	0,01	0,04	3,17
15	Fromage blanc	5	5	2,73	2,66	0,98	0,01	0,06	10,47
16	Cypriot Halloumi cheese	5	5	3,97	4,02	1,01	0,24	0,26	1,04
17	Traditional Slovak cheese from unpasteurised ewes' milk**	5	5	3,46	2,84	0,82	0,00	0,29	172,98
18	Natural ripening cheese (raw milk)	5	5	2,32	2,98	1,28	0,19	0,19	1,04
19	Non-matured cheese (raw milk)	5	5	3,28	3,36	1,02	0,01	0,00	0,42
20	Non-matured cheese (raw milk)	5	5	5,71	5,71	1,00	0,01	0,01	1,57
21	Non-matured cheese (raw milk)	5	5	4,43	4,38	0,99	0,02	0,01	0,77

22	Non-matured cheese (raw milk)	5	5	4,79	4,85	1,01	0,02	0,04	2,01
23	Non-matured cheese (raw milk)	5	5	5,34	5,35	1,00	0,01	0,02	1,33
24	Pasteurised cheese	5	5	2,57	2,66	1,04	0,00	0,00	1,12
25	Cheese	4	5	NA	3,61	NA	NA	0,35	NA
26	Cheese	5	5	3,41	3,15	0,92	0,37	0,45	1,19
27	Cheese	5	5	3,26	3,48	1,07	0,13	0,72	5,58
28	Cheese	5	5	3,25	3,58	1,10	0,18	0,04	0,24
29	Pecorino cheese	5	5	6,97	6,93	0,99	0,01	0,00	0,33
30	Ripened pecorino cheese	5	5	6,89	7,04	1,02	0,01	0,01	1,05
31	Tome cheese	5	5	5,24	5,62	1,07	0,15	0,11	0,73
32	Tome cheese	5	5	5,08	5,17	1,02	0,34	0,11	0,31
33	Demi-hard cheese from pasteurised milk	5	5	2,98	3,17	1,06	0,07	0,02	0,34
34	Fresh goat Tomme	5	5	4,42	4,24	0,96	0,02	0,04	2,12
*4 subsamples only									
**method 6888-1, enumeration level 100 cfu/g									

For the 34 samples as a whole, the measured mean counts for 10 and 25 gram test portion sizes were in the ranges 2.32-6.97 and 2.66-7.04 log cfu/g, respectively, indicating a similar range for both test portion sizes, but with an upward shift of approximately 0.2 log units for 10 gram test portion sizes compared to 25 gram test portion sizes.

The variance was estimated only for samples with 5 positive results. The variances for all samples ranked from 0.002 to 1.86. No clear difference between test portion sizes was seen.

5.2.2 RATIOS BETWEEN SAMPLE PORTION SIZES (DETERMINISTIC APPROACH)

As for *Listeria monocytogenes*, the difference of the two test portion sizes was investigated by comparing the ratios of log mean counts and variance obtained for 25 and 10 g test portion size (25/10 g). Ratios equal to 1.0 indicate no difference, ratios higher than 1.0 that the values were higher for 25 than for 10 gram portion size, and vice versa for ratios below 1.0. The results are shown in Table 2 and Figure 9.

The ratios of log mean counts for 10 and 25 g portion sizes were calculated for samples with 5 valid subsample results. Of the 31 samples, 17 had ratios higher than 1.0, 11 samples below 1.0 and 2 samples equal 1.00 (Table 2). The extreme values were 0.82 and 1.28, obtained for sample 17 and 18 (Table 2, Figure 9), while 28 of the samples had ratios within 0.90-1.10, indicating a

small, if any, difference between test portion sizes in term of measured log mean counts for the majority of samples.

The ratio of variance was in the range 0.006 to 7.96 (Tables 3, 4 and Figure 9). The ratios could be calculated for 31 samples. Among these, 17 samples had ratios above 1.0 and 14 samples below 1.0. The overall pattern in terms of variance was therefore a high variance, but no systematic difference between 10 and 25 gram test portion sizes.

Figure 9. Ratios of 10 gram and 25 gram portion sizes for log mean values and variances (σ^2) based on standard analyses of raw data in Excel. The sample numbers refer to Table 3.

Based on the analysis of raw data, no clear differences between test portion sizes could be seen for variance.

5.2.3 ANALYSES OF VARIANCE TAKING INTO ACCOUNT THE UNCERTAINTIES OF VARIANCE (PROBABILISTIC APPROACH)

As for *L. monocytogenes*, the difference between test portion sizes was further investigated using parametric bootstrap. This method takes into account the data below enumeration level as well as other uncertainties, estimates a range of the variance, which in turn gives the ratio of variances with a range of uncertainty.

The ranges of variance were estimated for all samples, both for 10 and 25 gram test portion sizes. The simulated patterns were as showed for *L. monocytogenes* in Figure 7. The results for each sample are given in more details for all samples in Annex 3.

The ratios of variances between 10 and 25 gram portion sizes, taking the uncertainty of variance into account, are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Ratios of variances for 10 versus 25 gram portion sizes, with the uncertainty of variances taken into account.

The results showed that only 6 of the samples had a ratio of variances different from 1.0, when the uncertainty in variance was taken into account. Among these, 4 samples had a ratio higher than 1.0 and 2 samples below 1.0. The samples with lowest counts (Figure 8) tended to have a higher ratio of variance than the others. The main pattern is however that 28 out of 34 samples show no significant difference in terms of variance between portion sizes.

6 DISCUSSION

The purpose of the present work was to investigate whether a change from 10 to 25 gram test portion size for Lm and CPS quantitative analysis would give more precise results and thereby more correct interpretation of analyses and better decisions towards conformity to food safety criteria. A previous study had shown that 100 gram test portion size gave less variation between subsamples than 10 gram portion size, but as analyses of large portion sizes require more work and higher costs of media, it was desired to investigate whether an increase to 25 gram portion size would be, on one hand, sufficient to reduce the variance between subsamples, and on the other hand, worth the extra costs of media compared to 10 gram sample portion size which is standard portion size for quantitative analyses today.

In the present work, the results of analyses of 46 naturally contaminated samples, 12 of *L. monocytogenes* and 34 for CPS, indicated that the variance between 10 and 25 gram test portion size was significantly different for only 8 samples. Among these, 6 samples gave a higher variance for 10 gram portion size and 2 samples for 25 gram test portion size. The overall pattern was that there was no clear difference between the portion sizes regarding the variance of the log mean counts of subsamples. The same result was obtained both (i) for classical and deterministic comparison of log means standard deviations and (ii) for the parameter bootstrap stochastic method. Based on the results of the present study, it can be concluded that a 25 gram test portion size is not likely to give more precise results than 10 gram test portion size for the studied food matrices.

There was, however, a large difference of enumeration results between subsamples for both test portion sizes. The differences between subsamples were larger than one log unit for the majority of samples. This diversity needs to be considered before a recommendation for test portion sampling can be given.

Theoretically, the large difference of enumeration values between subsamples could be due to measurement uncertainty or heterogeneity between subsamples. The measurement uncertainty for colony count techniques is normally within 0.5 log₁₀ unit, even when the analyses are carried out at different laboratories (Augustin & Carlier, 2006), as in this study. The observed range between subsamples in the present study is therefore larger than the expected measurement uncertainty. The contamination heterogeneity in naturally contaminated samples has been reported to be in the same range as observed in the present study (De Cesare et al, 2014, Jongenburger et al, 2015). A study of commercially produced and naturally contaminated salmon packed in 150 gram samples showed a difference between sealed packages of more than 3 log₁₀ units after storage for two weeks, even if the samples were from the same fish and processed with the same machine and personnel (Skjerdal et al 2014). Similar results have been obtained with heat treated chicken meat, where subsamples were taken from 2-kg packages with 5-8 cm distance between the sampling points: a range of subsample counts up to 2 log units was observed within each package. Some subsamples were even negative with qualitative analysis (Skjerdal et al, in prep). Sample portion sizes of 125 grams from the same material were also tested in the study and the measured counts were in all cases lower than the maximum value for individual subsamples. Based on these and other reported studies of naturally contaminated samples as well as observations at NRLs in several countries, the experience is that naturally contaminated samples, with solid matrices, are generally heterogeneous. For instance, the counts of staphylococci are often higher on the surface than in the core of cheeses (Cauquil et al,

2013; Macori et al, 2016). The challenge in test portion sampling is therefore to capture the test portions so it covers the heterogeneity of the sample. In this context, the outcome of the present and other studies is that it is more useful to collect the test portion from different parts of the food sample, rather than taking one larger test portion from only one point.

The optimum test portion size depends on the purpose of the analysis. For epidemiological purposes, it is useful to assess the ingested dose of a meal, which means that the peak values are of less importance than the average counts. If the purpose is to check against microbiological criteria in the legislation (EC Regulation 2073/2005), it is essential to detect counts above the legal limit, being 100 cfu/g for *L. monocytogenes* in ready-to-eat products and 1000 or 100 000 cfu/g for CPS in various products. For this purpose, it is important that the sample is not diluted, which will be the case if a large test portion size is taken from a product with contamination in only a small part of it. In the present study, the dilution effect was seen as up to 0.2 higher log₁₀ mean counts for 10-gram samples size than for 25-gram sample size.

To obtain the conformity status of a production batch, it is important that the sample units are taken from a large and representative part of the batch. It is also a purpose to keep the sampling at a limited level, both because of the costs and the amount of food used for sampling. When all these purposes of sampling are taken together, to cover the contamination heterogeneity, the best tradeoff seems to be to collect sample units from different parts of the food batch, and take several smaller subsamples to form the test portion, instead of taking one large test portion. The results obtained in the present work indicate that 10-gram test portion size is suitable.

7 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the present study, it can be concluded that a 25-gram test portion size is not likely to reduce measurement uncertainty, compared to a 10-gram test portion size for the studied food matrices. Furthermore, both test portion sizes gave very similar \log_{10} mean values.

The challenge in collecting the test portion is to capture the sample contamination heterogeneity. In this context, the outcome from the present and other studies is that it is more useful, to form the test portion, to take subsamples from different parts of the food sample, rather than taking one larger test portion from only one point.

As initially foreseen, EURL-CPS and EURL Lm will transmit this conclusion to ISO/TC 34/SC 9.

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9 ANNEXES

9.1 ANNEXE 1: SOP FOR EXPERIMENTS

II - Description of the protocol n°1 (CPS enumeration)

1. Food matrices to be tested

For CPS, the food matrices to be tested in the frame of the EC Regulation n°2073/2055 amended belong to the categories « milk and milk products » and « shelled and shucked products of cooked crustaceans and molluscan shellfish ». The minimal required mass of each sample is 250 g.

2. Material and methods

CPS enumeration will be performed once (no repetition of the analysis) by following the standardised method (EN ISO 6888-1 or EN ISO 6881-2) or a validated commercial method. Required material and culture media are described in the protocols or used standards.

3. Preparation of naturally contaminated samples

From a same food matrix naturally contaminated in CPS:

- Weigh 10 g taken in 5 spots, corresponding to one test portion. Repeat this 5 times, as to get 5 test portions of 10 g each.
- Weigh 25 g taken in 5 spots, corresponding to one test portion. Repeat this 5 times, as to get 5 test portions of 25 g each.

4. Samples analyses

Add 90ml of diluent such as Peptone Salt and/or Buffered Peptone Water to 10 g of samples.

AND

Add 225ml of diluent such as Peptone Salt and/or Buffered Peptone Water to 25 g of samples.

Mix 1 min.

Perform the analyses once. Perform high dilution rates (until 10^{-7} for instance when the CPS concentration is unknown).

III – Tracability and results of the protocol n°1 (CPS enumeration)

The experimentations being not performed at EURL, their numbering is not possible.

A result form is provided to the laboratories performing the analyses. This form includes the different required information.

The results treatment will be performed in the EURL CPS.

II - Description of the protocol n°2 (Lm enumeration)

1. Food matrices to be tested

Food matrices are ready-to-eat matrices, according to the Lm criteria of EC Regulation n°2073/2005 modified, naturally contaminated in *Listeria monocytogenes*. They can be stored several months at -18°C before analysis. The minimal required mass of each sample is 250 g.

2. Material and methods

Lm enumerations will be performed once (no repetition of the analysis) by following the standardised method (EN ISO 11290-2 with amendment) or a validated commercial method. Required material and culture media are described in the protocols or used standards.

3. Preparation of naturally contaminated samples

From a same food matrix naturally contaminated in Lm, perform 10 portions (5 portions of 10 g and 5 portions of 25 g) in the following manner:

- Weigh 10 g taken in 5 spots, corresponding to one test portion. Repeat this operation 5 times, as to get 5 test portions of 10 g each.
- Weigh 25 g taken in 5 spots, corresponding to a test portion. Repeat this operation 5 times, as to get 5 test portions of 25 g each.

4. Samples analyses

In each of the 10 blender bags, perform a 10-fold dilution.

Mix 1 min.

Perform the analyses once. Perform high dilution rates (until 10^{-6} for instance when the Lm concentration is unknown).

Collaboration : test portion « 25g/10g »

Figure of the detailed protocol

III – Tracability and results of the protocol n° 2 (Lm enumeration)

The experimentations being not performed at EURL, their numbering is not possible.

A result form is provided to the laboratories performing the analyses. This form included the different information to be noted.

The results treatment will be performed by EURL Lm.

9.2 ANNEXE 2: ESTIMATED DISTRIBUTIONS FOR *L. MONOCYTOGENES* IN SAMPLES AFTER PARAMETRIC BOOTSTRAP

The following figures illustrate estimated distribution for *L. monocytogenes* in RTE foods. The foods are coded from Lm1 to Lm12. The numbers are the same as in Table 1.

9.3 ANNEXE 3: ESTIMATED DISTRIBUTIONS FOR CPS IN SAMPLES AFTER PARAMETRIC BOOTSTRAP

The following figures illustrate estimated distribution for CPS in samples. The foods are coded from CPS1 to CPS34. The numbers are the same as in Table 3.


```
## Warning: The plyr::rename operation has created duplicates for the  
## following name(s): (`size`)
```